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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101069529 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant No 10038991].

Towards Inclusive Energy Communities in **Arnhem**

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Social Sciences & Humanities for Climate,
Energy aNd Transport Research Excellence

October 2024

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Suggested citation

SSH CENTRE Hub 3, 2024. *Towards Inclusive Energy Communities in Arnhem*, Cambridge: SSH CENTRE.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14763261>

Introduction

Energy communities (ECs) stand at the forefront of a sustainable energy transition, presenting an opportunity to democratise energy access and empower citizens. Despite their potential, ECs face significant practice and policy challenges in achieving an inclusive energy transition, that is, affordable, accessible, secure, reliable, and fair distribution of benefits and burdens for everyone¹. An inclusive approach prioritises removing barriers to participation in energy systems, guaranteeing that all community members can access and benefit from sustainable energy solutions. Inclusivity within ECs is a key factor to ensure that energy systems and processes will not become dominated by certain socio-demographic groups or elites and will not exclude marginalised groups, particularly those experiencing energy poverty, limiting their influence and participation in decision-making.

This report links ECs and inclusivity within the specific context of Arnhem, The Netherlands. Drawing from a comprehensive literature review on energy communities and inclusivity, alongside case studies of best practices from across Europe, this analysis also incorporates a detailed examination of Arnhem's existing energy policies and the current energy landscape, alongside interviews with representatives from Arnhem's municipality and the broader energy network. The report identifies key barriers, challenges and opportunities associated with participation in ECs. It explores the essential role that ECs play in Arnhem's energy transition and evaluates how the municipality can effectively support these communities. Consequently, the report offers practical and actionable recommendations for the Arnhem municipality to enhance inclusivity and establish robust ECs in the city. These recommendations further build on the contributions from the discussions and brainstorming sessions conducted during a two-day city workshop in April 2024.

1 Weijnen, M.P.C., Lukszo, Z., Farahani, S. (Eds.), 2021. Shaping an Inclusive Energy Transition. Springer International Publishing, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-74586-8>

Highlights from the two-day SSH-KB City Workshop in Arnhem, April 2024.

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1. Energy communities

The term ‘energy community’ is used worldwide as an umbrella term for all decentralised collective renewable energy initiatives involving different forms of citizen participation and control, without a primary commercial motive. An energy community engages with energy through activities such as energy generation, supply, consumption, storage or even energy efficiency services, through a variety of models like community energy initiatives, virtual power plants, community-owned renewable energy, prosumerism, and jointly acting renewable self-consumers, among others².

The European legislation outlines two distinct types of energy communities within the Clean Energy Package: Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) as per the Internal Electricity Market Directive 2019/944 and Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) according to the Renewable Energy Directive 2018/2001. These directives aim to foster and facilitate collective citizen engagement in the energy system by establishing a supportive legal framework.

ECs in European legislation are recognised as non-commercial entities aimed at delivering environmental, economic, or social benefits to their members and local areas, and not primarily financial profits. This distinction means commercial motives cannot drive an EC. While the specifics of these benefits are not detailed, ECs contribute to technology diffusion, improved household energy efficiency, energy poverty mitigation, and market participation. Importantly, governments are encouraged to leverage ECs in combating energy poverty, by “assessing the possibility to enable participation by households that might otherwise not be able to participate, including vulnerable consumers and tenants”³. Table 1 outlines the organisational requirements for CECs and RECs.

Table 1: Organisational requirements for an entity for establishing an energy community

	Citizen energy community (CEC)	Renewable energy community (REC)
Legal entity	The idea of energy communities in EU law is confined to those that have ‘a legal entity’. Although this requirement is relatively open and can, in theory, include medium-sized enterprises ⁴ , most energy communities take the form of a cooperative. This is also the case in the Netherlands, where practically all energy communities are a “coöperatie”, because this form of legal entity is believed to abide best with other requirements of the energy community.	
Open and voluntary participation	Any entity can become a member, from large to medium enterprises and from municipalities to household consumers.	Only medium and small enterprises, natural persons, and local authorities, including municipalities, may have membership.
Effective control⁵	Effective control is restricted to small enterprises, natural persons and local authorities (excluding medium and large enterprises).	All actors eligible for participation may exercise effective control, but it should remain autonomous from individual members.

2 Gruber, L., Bachhiesl, U., Wogrin, S., 2021. The current state of research on energy communities. *Elektrotechnik Informationstechnik* 138, 515–524. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00502-021-00943-9>; Bauwens, T., Schraven, D., Drawing, E., Radtke, J., Holstenkamp, L., Gotchev, B., Yildiz, Ö., 2022. Conceptualizing community in energy systems: A systematic review of 183 definitions. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 156, 111999. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111999>

3 Recital 67 RED II.

4 Recital 44 EMD 2019; see also article 22(4) RED II.

5 The EU Commission indicates that Member States should define effective control. Hence, it can differ from having majority voting rights to having enough voting power to wield significant influence over voting processes, or to decisive influence through positions held in the board; REScoop, Energy Communities under the Clean Energy Package. Transposition Guidance, 2020, 26.

An important stipulation in EU legislation is the requirement for energy communities to be established as legal entities: without this legal framework, an entity cannot be classified as an energy community. In the Netherlands, the majority of energy communities are cooperatives (“coöperatie”), as this legal entity aligns well with the broader requirements for energy communities. However, it is essential to note that not all energy cooperatives meet the criteria to be considered energy communities. For example, some cooperatives may primarily pursue commercial goals, such as allowing individuals to invest in shares for a solar park, with the expectation of earning a profit from the electricity sold on the market over the project’s lifespan. Since the primary purpose of energy communities should not be financial gain, mere financial participation by citizens does not suffice for an entity to qualify as an energy community. However, this distinction is currently not recognised in Dutch energy law.

Energy communities are required to prioritise environmental, social and economic community benefits. This means that at their core, energy communities must be fundamentally inclusive. Inclusiveness can manifest in various ways, from offering members affordable energy solutions to fostering robust and cohesive community ties. These activities may cover a broad spectrum, addressing diverse needs and contributions within the community to ensure comprehensive benefits. However, energy communities can vary in their commitment to inclusive practices, ranging from passive to active forms (see adjoining policy report on Inclusivity Framework for Energy Communities⁶). Different modes of inclusion and exclusion involve different forms of communication, attention to social difference, representation, civic engagement, regulatory procedures, and policies. Building trust is especially important to get people on board with energy communities. For energy communities to be truly beneficial, it is essential that participants see themselves as active contributors rather than passive recipients of imposed initiatives.

6 [Link to Inclusivity Framework for Energy Communities policy output](#)

2. Arnhem's energy landscape

Setting the stage: Arnhem's energy network and current policies

Arnhem is committed to addressing climate change, aligning with the EU's goal for climate neutrality by 2050 through its 'New energy made in Arnhem 2020-2030' (NemiA) programme. NemiA aims for a 61% reduction in the city's CO₂ emissions by 2030, along four strategic lines: 1) built environment, 2) sustainable mobility, 3) business & industry, 4) and large-scale generation. Arnhem's policy on energy communities aligns with its energy innovation theme, particularly enhancing plans for solar and wind energy infrastructure. As outlined in NemiA, the city aims for local ownership of these energy projects, in accordance with the city's Climate Agreement 2019⁷. Municipal support for energy communities leverages existing frameworks for both energy initiatives and social activities. The following overview presents the current state of energy communities and municipal collaborations in Arnhem, rather than providing a comprehensive summary of all municipal policies.

Energy initiatives in Arnhem feature an advanced network of diverse stakeholders including the municipality, social housing corporations, NGOs and citizens. While the municipality leads some projects, leadership can vary. Figure 1 presents a schematic overview of Arnhem's energy landscape, the various actors involved, and ongoing projects⁸.

⁷ L. Broere & E. Holsappel, Aan de slag met lokaal eigendom (RES West-Overijssel), 2021.

⁸ This overview is schematic and not exhaustive, as a more detailed discussion is needed to unpack the connections between the municipality, social housing corporations, NGOs, and citizens. For instance, it omits the provincial Programma Wijken van de Toekomst, which explores alternative heating solutions and supports initiatives like Hoogkamp Energie.

Figure 1: Arnhem’s energy landscape, mapping the various organisations and stakeholders involved and their relation.

The municipality of Arnhem plays a crucial role in the city's energy transition. With a strong focus on energy poverty, the municipality has aimed to take a neighbourhood-level approach to the clean energy transition. However, due to restrictive legal frameworks that affect household consumers and small businesses, energy actions currently focus more on larger commercial and business sectors, as one interviewee noted, “currently, it is more about business parks, because this is where the actions mostly take place” [female, municipality]. Nonetheless, the municipally led initiative in Saksen-Weimar is exploring “opportunities for collective generation and storage. Depending on where we are active, we involve local stakeholders” [male, municipality representative]. This initiative is yet in its preliminary stages, pending funding from the European Union.

A more firmly institutionalised policy set up is that of the AANjaagfonds. This municipal policy provides subsidies for citizen-led neighbourhood initiatives that contribute to energy and climate goals of the municipality, as explained by one municipality representative: “The AANjaagfonds contains €500.000 for three years to enable neighbourhood initiatives to work together on collective solutions on sustainability and improvements of the neighbourhoods. It can be on the household level, it can even be on greening” [male, municipality].

Rijn & IJssel Energiecoöperatie (REIJE) is the only operationalised energy community in the region of Arnhem. It is owned by citizens but stemmed from a municipal initiative to install wind turbines. The resulting windpark Koningspleij is partially owned by REIJE. The energy community also provides energy coaches, both professionals and volunteers, with municipal support, as explained by one representative: “There are quite a few people who go to individual house owners and provide support to improve the house in terms of its energy efficiency and that is being paid by the municipality” [female, REIJE].

In addition, energy coaching is also provided by the Energiebank. The Energiebank works solely for people with low income, so focuses on energy poverty. The Energiebank is interested in energy communities and, as one representative noted, investigating “possibilities to deliver energy also for us as Energy Bank in collaboration with other people of other companies” [male, Energiebank]. However, the organisation has developed around energy coaching, which remains its main activity. The municipality has facilitated the expansion of energy coaching by subsidising the Energiebank, significantly increasing its capacity to assist those in energy poverty—from 50 to approximately 1,200 individuals annually. To identify those in need, the Energiebank, in collaboration with the municipality, organises neighbourhood tables in five key areas. Additionally, for interventions that require physical modifications, the Energiebank partners with the neighbourhood fix brigades (‘buurtklusbedrijven’).

The neighbourhood fix brigades are also employed by DeBlauweWijkEconomie (or Spijkerenergie), another civil society-led initiative. It is active in a wide range of activities that address broader social and environmental needs and is centered around trust and community-building, generating employment and local welfare. DeBlauweWijkEconomie has also developed projects that leverage local by-products, such as using coffee waste to grow mushrooms, established a bicycle repair company, and developed initiatives like LED light distribution, which involved residents in hands-on, trust-based exchanges. To indicate the scale of this initiative: approximately 40 people are weekly involved in activities of DeBlauweWijkEconomie.

Arnhem's vibrant civil society is enriched by several other energy initiatives that have declared their interest in establishing energy communities. For instance, neighbourhood groups like GroenWest have formed a corporation, and in Paasberg, an association has been created to explore communal energy solutions, developing a significant community presence. Additionally, the Rosandepolder initiative aims to locally manage energy production, consumption and storage of approximately 40 houseboats, while Hoogkamp Energie focuses on establishing a neighbourhood heat network. Furthermore, the social housing corporation Volkshuisvesting is considering the potential benefits of forming an energy community: “An energy community could be an opportunity to realise collective benefits for the renters living in houses that are less favourable for solar energy” [female, Volkshuisvesting].

Despite the many active local initiatives, not all neighbourhoods in Arnhem have a vivid civil society. Some lack the social capital necessary to launch such projects. Targeted policies for these areas focus on social enhancement. A key example is the Arnhem-Oost project, aimed to sustainably improve living conditions and bolster social cohesion. Additionally, the Aanpak energiearmoede initiative pays significant attention to the specific needs of residents, integrating these considerations

into nearly all its activities. Yet, EC participation of vulnerable groups and those facing energy poverty remains a key challenge.

Role of ECs in Arnhem

Several initiatives mentioned previously could expand into energy communities. These communities may be established for environmental, economic, or social purposes, each providing a compelling reason for municipal support:

- **Environmental benefits:** The municipality of Arnhem can support energy communities that can help meet (renewable) energy goals and targets set by the central government or as stipulated in the NemiA report. Depending on their implementation, energy communities can mitigate network congestion (e.g. in the case of combined generation and storage).
- **Economic benefits:** Energy communities can generate financial benefits for their members by selling generated electricity on the energy market. While financial gains may not primarily be within the municipality's purview, profits can underpin socially oriented activities, adding a sustainable financial model to the community benefit.
- **Social benefits:** Energy communities can contribute to a just and inclusive transition. They can provide a plethora of services, such as a (re)distribution of wealth by allowing people to participate in an energy community who otherwise might not be able to do so, or provision of energy saving services to lower the energy bill of people experiencing energy poverty. Also, democratic ownership structures enhance inclusivity, building community trust and cohesion.

Bearing these principles in mind aids the municipality in deciding the nature and extent of support for ECs, while also addressing their specific challenges and barriers.

3. Challenges and barriers to inclusive ECs in Arnhem

The challenges and barriers to inclusive ECs in Arnhem, identified through interviews with representatives from Arnhem's energy network and during the city workshop, are presented below under key themes:

1. Administrative	
Regulatory barriers	Regulatory barriers are invoked as an important impediment in the establishment and operation of energy communities. The interaction with household consumers is difficult under current Dutch legislation. Electricity sharing, for example, is impossible. What the future Energy Act (Energiewet) brings in terms of regulatory advancements is complex.
Tenders	Tenders and bureaucratic processes can delay or block local initiatives. Tenders that are not specifically designed to harbour social goals and mainly contain financial requirements are favourable towards large exploiters and unfavourable to energy communities. For instance, the tender for the solar park Koningspleij was relatively broad in scope. As a result, a private company succeeded in securing the tender, a decision influenced by the lack of experience in integrating specific social and community-oriented goals at the time the tender was issued.
Municipal communication	<p>For other stakeholders involved in ECs, communicating with the municipality can be challenging due to the compartmentalised structure of its various departments, which often operate in silos. This fragmentation can lead to misalignments between the activities of social initiatives and the defined roles of different municipal sectors, complicating efforts to coordinate sustainability projects and social initiatives effectively, both with external stakeholders and within the municipality itself. Such structural divisions can also obstruct the process of securing community funding, further complicating collaboration.</p> <p>For the municipality, proactive communication with external stakeholders poses its own set of challenges. Although municipalities play a pivotal role in the heat transition, the reality is that social housing corporations, which own numerous properties, are crucial for ensuring extensive grid connections. However, ongoing renovations of rental properties with electric heat pumps—undertaken without municipal collaboration—can result in fewer connections to a planned heat network. This lack of coordination not only undermines the network's financial viability but also impedes broader sustainability efforts.</p>
2. Financial	
Project profitability	Profitability of energy projects is uncertain, particularly for heat networks, which may struggle to establish a robust business case. This issue is compounded by administrative barriers that hinder open communication, essential for securing connections to heat networks. Moreover, under prevailing market conditions, solar panel projects also face difficulties in achieving financial viability.
Affordability	Existing financial models for community energy projects do not always support widespread participation, especially from lower-income groups. The need for investments can be a significant barrier. For example, shares for the wind park Koningspleij were priced at €250 each, which could be prohibitive for some residents, while shares for solar panels were more accessible at €25 each.

3. Technical	
Network congestion	Network congestion and the capacity of existing infrastructure to support new energy systems is a recurrent technical challenge.
Complexity	Incorporating heat communities or combining electricity with storage significantly increases the complexity of energy projects. Acquiring the necessary expertise requires a considerable time investment, a challenge compounded by the fact that many local initiatives rely on volunteer governance. Furthermore, these projects typically necessitate collaboration among multiple stakeholders. Additionally, the technical intricacies often intersect with uncertainties regarding legal frameworks, adding another layer of complexity to project implementation.
4. Social & cognitive	
Discriminatory structures	People lacking resources, time, and space often prioritise other concerns over joining energy communities. Typically, those interested in energy communities tend to be older, technically educated males. Moreover, not everyone sees the value in becoming a member of an energy community, preferring the freedom to choose their own energy suppliers without the commitments such involvement entails.
Cognitive	<p>Economic and social disparities can exacerbate the difficulty in achieving equitable participation in energy projects. Lower-income groups often exhibit a lack of trust in institutions and scepticism towards energy communities, stemming from insufficient awareness of their benefits. This pattern is especially apparent among tenants from social housing projects and among renters. While energy communities present an opportunity to make the energy transition inclusive, engaging these groups necessitates building trust and knowledge.</p> <p>Ineffective communication strategies do not reach or properly engage all community members, often due to language barriers, accessibility issues, or simply unappealing messaging. The complexity of information and lack of tailored messaging to different segments of the population can prevent understanding and interest in ECs. Traditional approaches such as distributing leaflets and energy boxes (filled with energy saving products and tips) may not be the most effective method to attract interest. Instead, face-to-face interactions, although challenging, prove more successful in initiating meaningful conversations about energy communities. The key challenge lies in gaining access to these individuals' living spaces to start these discussions.</p>

While the challenges and barriers mentioned are widely recognised, their impact varies across different initiatives. For instance, an energy community may struggle with social inclusivity, e.g. due to an overrepresentation of homeowners (as opposed to renters), technically skilled individuals, males, and older people, prompting a need for strategies to include more vulnerable groups. Conversely, a social service initiative aiming to transition into an energy community might predominantly encounter administrative and financial challenges, such as securing funding, acquiring regulatory knowledge, and managing administrative tasks. In both scenarios, the nature of the help that might be needed differs.

Furthermore, different stakeholders encounter distinct barriers. The local municipality can struggle to integrate energy planning with broader urban development goals, grappling with bureaucratic delays while striving to address energy poverty swiftly. Energy cooperatives face operational challenges in scaling up and ensuring inclusivity, frequently constrained by the need for substantial initial investment and a stable policy environment, which may be lacking. Housing associations, while prioritising sustainability, must balance financial viability with building tenant trust, requiring more support from local governments and clearer regulations to enhance their participation in energy communities. Lastly, citizens and community groups aspire to greater control over local energy production and its benefits but often lack the resources or technical expertise necessary to initiate or sustain such projects.

4. Opportunities

Arnhem's broad energy network and diverse range of initiatives already underway present considerable opportunities for setting up successful and inclusive ECs that can address issues of energy poverty and the various barriers to participation identified. Key opportunities include:

Leveraging existing networks and partnerships

Establishing ECs through existing networks can enhance inclusivity and overcome representation barriers. For instance, Klimaatverbond's collaboration with Energie Samen utilises their established trust and frameworks to engage a broader demographic effectively. Moreover, the municipality can support inclusive ECs by forming public-private partnerships to manage initial investments and operations, offering membership to selected vulnerable households.

Utilising municipal initiatives and support

Municipal support, such as the AANjaagfonds, provides crucial financial and organisational backing, helping to overcome initial financial barriers for ECs. Funds such as this can support citizen-led sustainability initiatives, providing a structured pathway for ECs to integrate sustainable practices at the neighbourhood level. Moreover, initiatives can be targeted at landlords to invest in EC participation by sharing benefits with tenants, such as recovering part of the energy savings through rent adjustments.

Focusing on broader social goals and just transitions

Integrating social goals within ECs ensures inclusivity and addresses the engagement of vulnerable groups. Initiatives like the neighbourhood tables (working groups in neighbourhoods) increase social acceptance of alternative energy solutions. These groups could be fostered as a basis for further action. Further support can be ensured through differentiation in cost of shares for participation of pre-determined vulnerable groups. Projects like Arnhem-Oost and the Energiebank's focus on energy poverty serve as a model for incorporating social equity, making EC benefits accessible to all community segments.

Empowering local leadership and ownership

Promoting local leadership and ownership can increase trust and local engagement within ECs. The Rijn & IJssel Energiecoöperatie (REIJE), partially owned by citizens, and the citizen-led Spijkerkwartier, demonstrate the potential for ECs to thrive under community-driven leadership structures. The successful implementation of projects like communal LED light testing in Spijkerkwartier showcases how addressing cultural and social factors can enhance trust, project acceptance and participation.

Educational and capacity building programmes

Educational initiatives address informational and skill-related barriers by equipping citizens with the necessary knowledge and tools. Programmes like those offered by REIJE and the Energiebank not only educate but also empower residents to manage energy effectively in their homes.

Developing customised energy solutions

Customised energy solutions can better meet the unique needs of different community segments, enhancing community buy-in. In Spijkerkwartier, tailored initiatives for communal energy solutions underscore the effectiveness of addressing specific neighbourhood energy needs.

5. Recommendations for the municipality

The challenges and opportunities for ECs in Arnhem underscore the complexities involved in accommodating diverse forms of ECs and multiple stakeholders. While these may include the municipality, it may not necessarily take a leading role. Instead, ownership and collaboration often involve other parties. Hence, careful consideration is required by the municipality to understand *what* is required for a specific EC to be successfully setup and/or operational, and *how* it wants to provide that support. And for this, the municipality must determine its role within the EC. This decision-making process involves balancing the interests that an EC aims to serve, while also considering its organisational structure. To this end, below are outlined three key roles that the municipality can adopt to support inclusive ECs in Arnhem:

- **Knowledge broker:** in this role, the municipality serves as a source of information for ECs. It collects and disseminates data, resources, and success stories in an accessible and engaging manner, facilitating connections between ECs and potential resources. This role involves acting as an intermediary that bridges information gaps and inspires by showcasing innovative practices and opportunities within and beyond the local context.
- **Active supporter:** in its role as a supporter, the municipality provides comprehensive assistance to both emerging and established ECs. This support encompasses a range of resources, including material aid, financial backing, and organisational guidance. The aim is to actively enhance the operational capabilities of ECs, ensuring they have the necessary tools and funding to thrive. This role underscores the municipality's commitment to nurturing a supportive environment that enables ECs to flourish.
- **Initiator:** in this role, the municipality takes a proactive stance by leading and launching EC initiatives directly. This role positions the municipality as a catalyst for action, driving the development of new projects and encouraging widespread community participation. By leading from the front, the municipality sets a proactive example, demonstrating its dedication to sustainable community development and energy independence.

Below are outlined key actions that the municipality of Arnhem can take considering the identified challenges and barriers to foster inclusive ECs in each of these roles. Whilst focused on Arnhem, these suggestions are indeed applicable to other cities and municipalities:

Recommended actions for the municipality as Knowledge Broker of inclusive ECs

Administrative	
Establish information hubs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish centralised information hubs that simplify the complex regulatory and administrative processes for setting up and operating ECs. These hubs could provide step-by-step guides, case studies, and templates for required documentation, directly addressing the bureaucratic challenges highlighted in the case of tender processes and regulatory barriers.
Develop comprehensive inclusive EC guides	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop an introductory guide detailing all existing energy initiatives in Arnhem, assistance and subsidising channels, and the administrative steps that need to be taken (and how). This can include consulting internal and external experts about policy and spatial rules and requirements, and weighing their advice.⁹ This should be available in multiple languages and distributed through social organisations and online platforms to ensure accessibility. These resources could include success stories and strategies from other municipalities, directly addressing the challenge of discriminatory structures within ECs.
Regular stakeholder workshops and tailored outreach programmes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct workshops and training sessions for EC initiators on navigating municipal processes, including tender applications and compliance with energy laws. This will improve communication and alignment between EC initiatives and municipal requirements. Initiate outreach programmes that specifically target underrepresented groups.
Advocate for inclusive policy making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The municipality can also advocate for more inclusive energy policies at higher government levels by presenting data and case studies from local EC success projects.
Financial	
Subsidy and investment promotion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop comprehensive guides and regular newsletters that detail available local, national, and EU funding opportunities. Regularly update and promote a comprehensive list of subsidies and investment programmes specifically tailored for energy communities, focusing on those that support the inclusion of vulnerable groups. Specifically target building owners who rent out houses through the regulation/promotion of systems in which they invest in EC participation and share the benefits with their tenants (e.g. part of the gained energy savings is recovered through the rent) Promote a differentiation in cost of shares for participation.
Financial navigation workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct workshops aimed at building owners and EC initiators on navigating financial opportunities and challenges in EC setups. These should cover topics like investment in renewable energy assets, sharing benefits with tenants, and understanding municipal, national, and EU funding landscapes.

⁹ Kluskens, N., Alkemade, F., & Höffken, J. (2024). Beyond a checklist for acceptance: understanding the dynamic process of community acceptance. *Sustainability Science*, 19(3), 836, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-024-01468-8>.

Technical	
Technology sharing platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch an online platform or series of workshops that share successful technical implementations of energy projects within Arnhem, providing case studies, best practices, and troubleshooting advice. This platform should include information on integrating advanced energy solutions like storage technologies and heat communities.
Social	
Multilingual communication resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure that all promotional material and operational guidelines for ECs are available in multiple languages. This would include the translation of essential documents and the provision of translation services at community meetings or events.
Community engagement platforms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up online and offline platforms where community members can engage with EC initiatives, ask questions, and provide feedback. This would help address the cognitive barriers related to distrust and scepticism by fostering a transparent and interactive approach to community energy projects.
Inclusivity workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer regular training sessions and workshops on how to make energy communities more inclusive. These should provide practical tips on everything from hosting accessible meetings (e.g., making locations easily accessible for people with mobility issues, including formats for people with less social skills, technical know-how, reading disabilities, or limited access to computers/smart tech, etc.) to engaging a diverse member base, ensuring that ECs are welcoming and accessible to all, particularly vulnerable groups.
Cognitive	
Educational resources and events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a resource library accessible both online and in community centres that includes materials on EC benefits, setup processes, and energy-saving tips. • Host community events that allow for the sharing of ideas and success stories, which can help demystify the processes involved in joining or starting an EC. • Organisations that work on inclusivity can be invited for inspirational talks and provide relevant suggestions on necessary actions and focal points.
Awareness campaigns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop targeted awareness campaigns that educate the public about the benefits and operations of ECs. These campaigns should use easy-to-understand language and be disseminated through local neighbourhood initiatives, social media, and public workshops. • Distribute a consultation survey on the specific needs of pre-determined vulnerable groups which could be met by an EC and translate them into concrete actions for EC initiatives.
Risk management and flexible commitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote opt-out options with EC initiators, to reduce reluctance to join due to fear of long-term commitments

Recommended actions for the municipality as Supporter of inclusive ECs

Administrative	
Streamlined permitting process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simplify and expedite the permitting process for ECs by providing dedicated support through the municipal office. This could involve prioritizing applications related to ECs and offering one-on-one guidance to navigate the bureaucratic processes effectively.
EC facilitation office	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish a municipal office dedicated to energy communities, which acts as a central point of contact for navigating municipal and regulatory processes. This office could provide personalised assistance, matchmaking support to connect local ECs with other relevant stakeholders and organisations, and help streamline administrative procedures for EC members and initiators.
Dedicated EC project managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assign project managers at the neighbourhood level who specialise in EC initiatives to assist with administrative challenges. These managers would act as liaisons between ECs and various municipal departments to ensure smooth communication and timely resolution of issues.
Regulatory support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide regulatory support, e.g., granting temporary legal status and additional benefits to encourage EC participation and investment. This can include tax breaks, expedited permitting processes, or direct financial rewards for residents and businesses that contribute to or invest in ECs. Implement regulations that mandate and incentivise diversity in Energy Communities, offering financial benefits to ECs that achieve varied membership.
Financial	
Direct financial support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offer direct grants or subsidies to ECs, to engage in systematic co-creation efforts during their setup phase, particularly those focusing on integrating vulnerable populations or utilising innovative technologies. Targeted subsidies can provide financial assistance to those facing energy poverty.
Investment matching programmes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create programmes that match investments made by EC members, reducing the financial burden on individuals, and enhancing the appeal of joining or investing in ECs.
Advance energy bill payments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement a system where the municipality can advance the payment of energy bills for vulnerable groups, offering them repayment plans that align with their financial capabilities.
Prosumer energy donation initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate the redistribution of surplus energy from prosumers to households experiencing energy poverty, enhancing community support and energy equity.
Technical	
Technical advisory services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide technical advisory services to ECs, helping them design, implement, and manage complex energy projects, such as integrating renewable energy sources with existing infrastructure or implementing new storage technologies.
Support for innovative energy solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offer technical and financial support for pilot projects that explore new technologies or business models in energy communities, particularly for heat networks and energy storage.

Social	
Inclusive community engagement initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fund and organise community engagement activities that promote the benefits of joining ECs and encourage diverse membership. These could include informational fairs, workshops, and demonstration projects that showcase successful local ECs.
Social support hubs and inclusion programmes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop and support programmes aimed at increasing the participation of underrepresented groups in ECs. This could include initiatives that promote gender diversity, involve different age groups, and integrate people from various socio-economic backgrounds. • A support system for EC initiators could encourage them to establish ECs with member diversity. • Create spaces for such engagements.
Partnerships with third parties and neutral intermediaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish closer cooperation with social housing companies and local neighbourhood initiatives (e.g., through EC project managers and neighbourhood ambassadors) to identify vulnerable households, develop tailor-made energy solutions that are accessible to all residents, particularly those in vulnerable situations, and provide assistance where needed. • Partner with well-regarded local entities such as banks, universities, and religious organisations to validate project feasibility and endorse benefits to the community. Collaborate with social workers and other non-municipal agents to facilitate outreach activities without a governmental “stamp” and provide financial and administrative support.
Cognitive	
Education and training programmes	<p>Offer ongoing education and training for EC initiators, members, and the public to increase understanding of energy systems, the benefits of EC participation, and how to engage effectively with these systems.</p> <p>Expand training for local unemployed residents to become energy coaches or handypersons, providing neighbourhood-level energy assistance. Leverage expertise from organisations like Energiebank and REIJE to develop ‘train the trainer’ programmes, enhancing community support capabilities.</p>
Neighbourhood helpdesks	<p>Set up helpdesks at a neighbourhood level that assist (vulnerable) members with specific questions, problems, and necessary paperwork. An open-door policy in multiple languages, manned by local volunteers, can increase more varied participation.</p>
Neighbourhood ambassadors	<p>Develop a programme that identifies and trains neighbourhood ‘EC ambassadors’ (particularly from vulnerable groups) who can advocate for EC benefits and participation within their communities through visible promotion and action, thereby building trust and encouraging wider engagement.</p> <p>Ensure their financial support.</p>

Recommended actions for the municipality as Initiator of inclusive ECs

Administrative	
Integrated EC office and task force	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish a dedicated office or task force within the municipality to lead the development and management of ECs. This office or cross-department task force would be responsible for all administrative aspects, from the initial planning stages to execution, ensuring streamlined processes and compliance with regulatory frameworks.
Cross-departmental collaboration framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a framework for collaboration among different municipal departments (e.g., environment, finance, urban planning) to facilitate the integration of EC initiatives into broader city planning and development strategies.
Invest in municipal heat networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allocate municipal resources to develop and expand heat networks, focusing on reducing the upfront investment costs and administrative complexities for residents, particularly in vulnerable neighbourhoods. This can serve as a foundational element (as it represents an inclusive form of energy sharing that must include all residents to be profitable) to encourage participation in broader EC projects.
Mandate connection to neighbourhood EC heat networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enact legislation requiring all new land developments and building constructions within the municipality to connect to existing neighbourhood EC heat networks (alleviating any administrative and financial burdens through required support), while maintaining voluntary participation in the network's specific services.
Utilise public spaces for EC initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement policies to open up all municipal roofs and public spaces for use in EC projects. This should include stipulations in tender documents that mandate inclusivity in EC initiatives, ensuring that these public assets are leveraged to benefit the entire community.
Establish diversity-driven regulations for ECs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement proactive regulations that include subsidies and incentives for EC initiators to promote member diversity, e.g., providing financial advantages to ECs that successfully integrate diverse demographic participation.
Financial	
Municipal investment in EC infrastructure and assets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actively invest in essential infrastructure for ECs, such as renewable energy installations and smart grids, to kickstart projects and reduce upfront costs for community members. Pre-finance investments in renewable energy assets or EC shares for predetermined vulnerable groups, with structured repayment plans tied to the energy savings achieved or through low-interest or zero-interest loans.
Establish municipality-led ECs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set up an EC where the municipality initially manages all asset investments and operational aspects. Membership would be specifically offered to predetermined vulnerable households who share in the benefits, such as lower energy costs, with a planned transition to member ownership after achieving operational stability.
Public-private partnership models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initiate and structure public-private partnerships to fund and manage EC projects, utilising municipal resources to attract and secure additional private investment.

EC micro-donation programme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set up and promote a system within ECs allowing members to voluntarily donate a small amount per kWh of energy used (e.g., 0.5, 1, or 2 cents). Offer tax deductions to encourage these contributions. Redirect the collected funds to local organisations that support households in fuel poverty and help integrate them into sustainable energy initiatives.
Technical	
Municipal-led pilot projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Launch innovative pilot projects that test new technologies or approaches in energy community development, e.g. heating districts, and energy storage systems. These projects can serve as benchmarks and provide valuable insights for scaling up successful practices.
Technical support units	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set up technical support units within the municipality that provide expertise and guidance on complex technical issues related to energy generation, storage, and distribution.
Social	
Inclusive community engagement strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organise and lead extensive community engagement and consultation programmes to ensure that EC initiatives are well-received and supported by residents. These should focus on education, awareness, and transparency to build trust and encourage active participation. Organise activities that increase the visibility and engagement of community members, particularly those who feel marginalised or invisible. This can include neighbourhood meals, native kitchens, language lessons, multi-language events, children's activities etc. Involve citizens in municipal energy planning to develop a comprehensive roadmap that includes crucial project execution details such as timing, location, and financing, ensuring these elements align with community needs and expectations.
Facilitate inclusive design in EC setup	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actively participate in the initial setup stages of ECs as an intermediary or moderator, ensuring the deployment of high pre-set inclusivity standards through which the needs and concerns of vulnerable groups are addressed and integrated into the final design of the ECs.
Establish a community buddy system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement a buddy system that pairs residents based on complementary skills and needs to facilitate mutual assistance on small tasks. This could involve matching individuals who can offer transportation with those who have mobility challenges, or tech-savvy youths with older residents needing help with digital tasks.
Cognitive	
Training and capacity building	<p>Set up training for local unemployed residents to become energy coaches or handypersons, providing neighbourhood-level energy assistance. Leverage expertise from organisations like Energiebank and REIJE to develop 'train the trainer' programmes, enhancing community support capabilities.</p>
Empowerment initiatives	<p>Set up (empowerment) initiatives aimed at enhancing technical knowledge and skills, specifically targeting women, migrants, renters, and energy poor households.</p> <p>Train and deploy neighbourhood ambassadors and local volunteers who facilitate low-threshold community events, helping to break down barriers to participation due to lack of knowledge or scepticism. enable them to handle complex aspects of ECs, including administrative tasks. Training should also be provided on how to keep EC processes inclusive.</p>

6. General SSH policy recommendations for inclusive ECs

In navigating the evolving landscape of energy communities, a strategic and inclusive approach is essential for fostering equitable and sustainable energy systems. This case study and the Inclusivity Framework (as an adjoining output of the SSH Centre KB programme) can serve as a useful guide for municipalities across Europe to improve inclusivity in their practices and policies for ECs. To this end, key recommendations include:

- **Establishing clear and explicit definitions, terminologies, and understandings of inclusivity** by revising and reframing current narratives, languages, and structures in EU legislation and organisational policies on energy communities.
- **Ensuring an intersectional approach to inclusivity analyses, monitoring and evaluation:** local authorities can help in developing policies and standards for all new energy communities to include intersectional inclusivity approaches in their design and operation: making expertise on intersectionality and EDI (equity, diversity and inclusion) available and setting it as a requirement for those involved in key decision-making within energy initiatives and energy communities, including those tasked with data collection, analysis, monitoring and operation.
- **Closing important data gaps** on different forms of representation, as well as different forms of vulnerabilities and discrimination e.g., based on class, income, racism, migration status, disability, gender, age, indigeneity.
- **Institutionalising inclusive practices** by developing policies and legal frameworks that specifically target inclusivity and equity within energy projects. Integrating inclusivity targets, frameworks and checklists into project design, operation and consultations.
- **Creating enabling conditions for inclusive participation and transformative action** by targeting social, economic and political barriers to participation, for example through fiscal measures, legislation, low-income quotas and support mechanisms (highlighted below). Citizen engagement and participation formats need to be barrier-free, i.e. using simple, accessible (local) language, sign language, ensuring safety of spaces and transport, provisions for financial support to facilitate participation where necessary as well as timing participation formats in line with participants' schedules etc. The more inclusive the EC the greater potential for transformative social impacts.
- **Ensuring accountability and transparency** in processes and decision-making, which will indirectly benefit a more inclusive approach by enabling community trust. This can be achieved through better accountability mechanisms such as open reporting on actions, independent audits for energy projects and establishing clear channels for community feedback and grievances.
- **Providing support mechanisms by** increasing anticipatory action and promoting initiatives on social protection to better cushion the vulnerabilities from energy poverty that impact inclusion. Improving access to financial resources for vulnerable citizens but also local civil society that supports and advocates for the rights of vulnerable and marginalised groups. Making funding modalities more flexible, needs-based, and long-term (e.g., zero or low interest rate credit programmes, direct subsidies and tax exemptions for those ECs that reach a certain diversity/vulnerability threshold) and creating spaces for and expanding networking opportunities for civil society.

Acknowledgements

This report is an outcome of the SSH CENTRE (*Social Sciences and Humanities for Climate, Energy and Transport Research Excellence*) Knowledge Brokerage (KB) Programme, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme [grant No 101069529] and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant No 10038991]. The project aims to support cross-sectoral collaboration and empower citizens and networks to develop socially innovative solutions for the EU's climate transition, as well as strengthening SSH-STEM collaboration, transdisciplinary policy advice, inclusive engagement and SSH communities across Europe. More information on the project is available via its website.

The presented report is the output of the KB initiative focused on the theme of **energy communities**, developed in response to the need expressed by the Arnhem municipality in the Netherlands to ensure citizen engagement in energy transition processes, especially among citizens who experience energy poverty and have limited influence on and participation in decision-making.

Adjoining material

[Inclusivity Framework for Energy Communities](#)
[Serious Game webpage](#)

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Energy and Transport Research Excellence

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101069529 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant No 10038991].